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A Study on Teacher's Job Satisfaction in Singapore Secondary Schools

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ABSTRACT

Teacher job satisfaction is a vivacious area of study which signpost different variables and its influence on teachers working performance. Using the 2018 Teaching and Learning International Survey data shown that Singapore is among the countries where teachers job satisfaction is higher compared to other countries. Little is known on what are the variables that contribute to the teacher's job satisfaction in Singapore secondary schools which can be drawn as a lesson to other countries. This study investigated teacher's job satisfaction with working environment and teachers job satisfaction with profession. The study found that teachers are satisfied with both working environment and teaching profession. Furthermore, there was a statistical mean difference of gender in both teacher's job satisfaction working environment and teacher's job satisfaction with profession. In case of multiple linear regression, the study found that two independent variables selected such as satisfaction with working environment and with profession has equal significant contribution on the teacher's job satisfaction in Singapore secondary schools.

Keywords

Job satisfaction, Teachers, Secondary schools, Singapore.

1. Introduction

Job satisfaction refers to an orientation of emotions that employees have towards their role in performing work in an organization (Raziq & Maulabakhsh, 2015). Also, it can be defined as an integrated set of psychological and physiological conditions that motivate an employee to admit whether they are satisfied with a job or not. Job Satisfaction is the vital component for employee motivation and reassurance towards better job performance (Baah & Amoako, 2011). High job satisfaction of the employee can reflect their job performance and low job satisfaction can reflect how the job performance can be affected in the organization.

Teacher's job satisfaction plays a crucial role in teachers' effort, attitudes, and confidence in daily work with students and other education stakeholders (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2007). Exploring teachers' job satisfaction is imperative as it has strong implications for teachers' due to its impacts on student academic achievement, attrition, retention, commitment to education goals and job performance (Kyriacou, 2001; Zafarullah & Perti, (2019). High teacher job satisfaction has an unswerving impact on teachers, schools, and students in general. Several researches articulated that there is a positive relationship between teacher job satisfaction and teacher performance in the school (Renzulli, Parrott and Beattie, 2011).

Historically, Singapore is among the countries which have best education in the world (Torres, 2018) referring to PISA assessment framework from the OECD. The main key value in their education system is that "teachers are the core of education system". Singapore is staunch to nurturing and motivating teachers to grow and reach their personal and professional development. Teachers are satisfied with various factors in the schools such as working environment, salary, profession, class autonomy etc., In TALIS data 2013 specified that teachers in Singapore are satisfied with their job by 88%. However, almost half the teachers which is 46% compared with the TALIS average of 32% wonder if they could choose another career or profession, this reflecting how much Singapore teachers are satisfied with the job. This is the reason why a TALIS report has shown 82% of the teachers could still choose to be a teacher in Singapore, this percent is more than the TALIS average which is 78% (OECD, 2013).

Therefore, there is a need to assess teachers job satisfaction in Singapore based on the recent TALIS data of 2018. This data helped to analyze different factors that contributes to teacher's job satisfaction in Singapore. The results will draw a lesson to other developed and developing countries.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Job satisfaction is directly affected by various psycho-social factors and physiological factors such as working condition, autonomy, profession, salary etc., In Singapore, 89% of teachers are satisfied with their job (average of 90%-OECD); they are satisfied by several factors in the school (OECD 2018). These factors contribute to the job satisfaction which have a positive impact to teachers' attitudes towards their working performance. Due to the high level of teacher's job satisfaction in Singapore, there is a need of assessing which factors has influenced teacher's satisfaction. So, this study needs to exhume how working environment and teaching profession influence teacher's job satisfaction in secondary school teachers in Singapore. The study used inferential statistics to investigate and measure the variables that contributing to teacher's job satisfaction in Singapore secondary schools.

1.3 Research questions

- i. What is the correlation of teacher's satisfaction with working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession?
- ii. What is gender difference on satisfaction working environment and satisfaction with profession?
- iii. Does teacher's satisfaction with working environment, with profession, educational level, gender and age have an influence on their job satisfaction?

1.4 Research hypothesis

- i. H0 There is correlation between teacher's satisfaction with working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession
H1 There is no correlation between teacher's satisfaction with working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession
- ii. H0 There is statistical mean difference regards to how gender differ in satisfaction working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession
H1 There is no statistical mean difference regards to how gender differ in satisfaction working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession
- iii. H0 There is a significant model that predict satisfaction with working environment, teachers' satisfaction with profession, educational level, gender and age have an influence on job satisfaction
H1 There is no a significant model that predict satisfaction with working environment, teachers' satisfaction with profession, educational level, gender and age have an influence on job satisfaction

1.5 Key concept

Job satisfaction; refers to the sense of fulfillment and gratification that teachers experience through their work as a teacher. Teacher satisfaction depend on the different motive which can be extrinsic and intrinsic factors that influence someone to became satisfied or not (Watt and Richardson, 2008). However, TALIS 2018 aimed to accomplish the following factors which have positively correlation with job satisfaction;

- Repeat and improve the indicators of overall job satisfaction and teacher perceptions
- Value of Teaching profession
- Add new material on teachers' views on the factors that would increase their job
- Satisfaction and societal perception of the value of the profession
- Teachers attrition
- Teacher well-being and stress.

TALIS provides opportunity for analysis and comparison of job satisfaction at the teacher level in relation to school climate, class autonomy, teachers profession, working environment, teaching practices, leadership, and relationships with stakeholders. Therefore, among these factors, this study chooses to assess how teacher's work environment and teaching profession impact teacher's job satisfaction.

2. Literature review

As different institutions aimed at improving their productivity and ceasing employee turnover as well as reducing their stress, the studies on job satisfaction become significant. Analytically, job satisfaction measures an individual contentedness in their job. The studies of [Sunal, Sunal and Yasin \(2011\)](#) defined the term as a degree of fulfillment which an individual has; it can be either negative or positive attitude toward their work. Personal fulfillment can be either intrinsic or extrinsic satisfaction which depend on the job environment and circumstances ([Asrar-ul-Haq, Kuchinke & Iqbal, 2017](#)). Subsequently, a person's job satisfaction affects organization productivity through working performance. Thus, the topics of and individual job satisfaction has been conspicuous topics among organization leaders.

Teachers are the indispensable for sustaining the development of education system in a country. Teachers job satisfaction of teachers are essential for continuing growth of education system all over the world ([Sirima & Poipoi, 2010](#)). There are several factors of teacher's job satisfaction which have been found in different studies such as promotional opportunities, remuneration, working environment, organization support, workers cooperation, ineffective school management and profession development ([Bascia & Rottmann, 2011](#)). Many scholars identified three main factors for teacher's job satisfaction in the working place which are relating to (i) Incentives (ii) Working environment and (iii) Profession ([Nyamubi, 2017](#); [Buckley, Schneider & Shang \(2005\)](#); [Tillman & Tillman \(2008\)](#); [Watson \(2006\)](#); [Huysman \(2008\)](#); [Bowman & Rajani \(2009\)](#); [Tickle, Chang & Kim, 2011](#)); [Russel, Gleason-Gomez, & Williams 2010](#) [Tomazevic, Seljak & Aristovnik \(2014\)](#), [Sirin, \(2009\)](#), [Kumari, Joshi & Pandey \(2014\)](#), [Sohail & Huang \(2013\)](#) and [Sahito & Vaisanen \(2017\)](#)). These factors are promoting and sustaining teachers to stay motivated and satisfied with their professional development.

[Johnson, Kraft and Papay \(2012\)](#) examined on the impact of school working environment on teacher's job satisfaction in the US context. The study discovered that the factor of working environment is among the employee's satisfaction in the working place, this factor includes school culture, supportive environment, respect, and managerial support. Furthermore [Casuneanu \(2020\)](#) examined the link between professional development, working environment, working time and autonomy; the result shown that there is a direct impact between working environment, job satisfaction as well as job performance. [Houtte \(2006\)](#); [Chughtai \(2003\)](#) revealed that the teachers are more satisfied with working environment and teaching profession. Additionally, [Osakwe \(2014\)](#); [Johari, Tan & Zulkarnain \(2018\)](#) specified that building a conducive working environment in teaching profession rise job satisfaction level that boost teachers job performance hence it augments student performance.

Teaching profession is one among the important factor which cause teachers job satisfaction. The study of [McCarthy, Lambert, Crowe and McCarthy \(2010\)](#) argued that the school management plays a great role in increasing teachers' satisfaction with profession. In most of the developing countries and some of the developed countries. In most of developing countries teachers have been grouching on how their dissatisfied with their teaching profession ([Msuya, 2016](#)) not only in developing countries but also in some of the developed countries especially in rural areas. This perception causes many teachers to lose interest hence to

increase teacher's attrition, turn over and absenteeism in their schools especially in public schools. Hereafter affect school's performance due to ineffective working performance that affect teaching and learning process. These factors play a momentous role in prompting teacher working performance which has direct impact on teaching quality. In 2018 TALIS data has shown how Singapore is among of leading country with high level of teacher's job satisfaction. Thus, it is important to survey how the factors of teacher's job satisfaction with working environment and teachers job satisfaction with profession contribute to secondary school teacher's job satisfaction.

2.2 Theoretical perspective

This paper used ERG theory which developed by Clayton Alderfer 1972, modified by Maslow Hierarchy of Needs from five (5) factors to three (3) factors of motivation (Mitchell, 1982). ERG theory is an abbreviation of "E" stand for existence which relays on psychological and physical survival, "R" is relatedness which conveys sense of belonging and relationship in the community and "G" stand for Growth which means fulfillment, self-development, sense of attaining human potential. Individuals are motivated by numerous levels of needs in a related environment that may cause level of satisfaction or not (Thangal, Shafie, Yunos, Hamid, Sidik, & Azman 2021).

Also, Maslow highlighted that an individual need to be satisfied with one level before moving to another level, for instance safety needs before social needs (Mitchell 1982). His concept is contrary to Alderfer (1972) who disagreed and provoked that an individual doesn't need to be satisfied with existence need before being motivated by their relatedness needs. This implies that the sense of being accepted by the community and strengthening good relationship is an essential factor for satisfactions. Tabancali (2016) found that, the satisfaction level varies according to the various factors which motivate personal and professional development. This paper exposed the influence of these two variables; teachers' satisfaction with working environment (physiological) and teachers job satisfaction with the profession which relate with relatedness and growth in ERG theory. These variables helped to investigate the motivated factors of teachers' job satisfaction in Singapore secondary schools.

3. Methodology

3.1 Source of Data

This report uses data collected from a large sample of teachers in the Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) 2018 was conducted by Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). This study aimed to provide in depth information about education system and practice of secondary school teachers in Singapore. The data contain significant information concerning teachers job satisfaction, professional development, school climate, self-efficacy and several demographic variables.

3.2 Sample selection

This study selected Singapore as a case study of teacher’s job satisfaction in secondary school. However, the selection of this case follows the following criteria; i) Singapore has a best educational system which consider teacher as “core” of education reform and ii) reason is how TALIS data indicated high teacher’s job satisfaction in various factors.

3.3 Measured variables

3.4 Data analysis

Question one used bivariate correlation between teacher’s satisfaction with working environment and teacher’s satisfaction with profession. Question two used t-test analysis through compared mean, whereby gender differences in satisfaction working environment compared with satisfaction in profession. And lastly, question three the multiple regression was used to predict linear multiple regression model. The model predicted how teachers job satisfaction influenced by satisfaction with working environment, teachers’ satisfaction with profession, educational level through controlling gender and age.

4. Results

This part presents the findings of the study. The findings are presented based on the formulated research questions and objectives. The study presented descriptive statistics aimed at showing the overview of secondary school teachers in Singapore. Then, inferential statistics aimed to show their status of job satisfaction through the presentation of correlation, t-test analysis and multiple regression model.

4.1.1 Demographic Information

Percentage distribution of gender				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	
Valid	Female	2102	64.1	64.1
	Male	1178	35.9	35.9
	Total	3280	100.0	100.0

Table 4.1.1 above shown the percentage distribution of gender among the respondent group in the study. By considering that information which indicated that 64.1% were female and 35.9% were male. The data exposed that female were greater than male for 28.2% difference. Therefore, the studied sample population in Singapore reveal that female teachers are more that male teachers in secondary schools.

Percentage distribution of respondents' highest level of formal education completed					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid					
	Below <ISCED 2011 Level 6>	168	5.1	5.1	5.1
	<ISCED 2011 Level 6>	2387	72.8	73.0	78.1
	<ISCED 2011 Level 7>	693	21.1	21.2	99.3
	<ISCED 2011 Level 8>	24	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	3272	99.8	100.0	
Missing	Omitted or invalid	8	.2		
	Total	3280	100.0		

Table 4.1.3 above indicate highest level of formal education completed among Singapore secondary school teachers. The data indicated that out of 3280 teacher's majority of them have bachelor degree which is 73%, followed by 21.2% of teachers who have master's or equivalent level then there are 5.1% of teachers who have formal education level below bachelor degree and there is only 0.7% of teachers who have doctoral or equivalent level. This means that mostly of the teachers in Singapore are well educated as data indicated above.

Table 4.1.4: Percentage distribution of the Teacher Age Groups					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Under 25	98	3.0	3.0	3.0
	25-29	693	21.1	21.1	24.1
	30-39	1261	38.4	38.4	62.6
	40-49	820	25.0	25.0	87.6
	50-59	318	9.7	9.7	97.3
	60 and above	90	2.7	2.7	100.0
	Total	3280	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.4 above indicated the teachers age groups of the respondent. The data presented that, the majority of respondent were between the ages of 30 to39 with 38.4%, followed by teachers age group of 40 to 49 with 25%, then 25 to 29 with 21.1%, also there were 3% of the teachers age group who are under 25 and lastly, there are age group of 60 and above with 2.7%

4.2: Inferential statistics

i. **H0** There is no correlation between teacher's satisfaction with working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession

H1 There is correlation between teacher's satisfaction with working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession

		Job satisfaction with work environment,	Job satisfaction with profession,
Job satisfaction with work environment	Pearson Correlation	1	.477**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
Job satisfaction with profession	Pearson Correlation	.477**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The intention of this hypothesis was aimed to investigate the correlation between teacher's satisfaction with environment and satisfaction with profession. The data found that there is a positive relationship among teacher's satisfaction with work environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession whereby $r=0.477$, $p<0.01$. Therefore, H1 was accepted, this exposed that teachers are satisfied with both working environment of their school also their profession it may be due to the good support that they receive from their school leader.

ii. **H0** There is statistical mean difference regards to how gender differ in satisfaction working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession

H1 There is no statistical mean difference regards to how gender differ in satisfaction working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession

Table 4.2.2: Independent sample-T-test

		Gender - T	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Job satisfaction with work environment	Female		2079	11.8440310	2.02826036	.04448324
	Male		1166	11.9554668	2.25814845	.06613071
Job satisfaction with profession	Female		2082	11.3661068	1.80283529	.03951079
	Male		1167	11.4276835	1.85818248	.05439424

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Job satisfaction with work environment, teacher / Metric (All)	Equal variances assumed	12.604	.000	-1.441	3243	.150	-.11143580	.07733553	-.26306725	.04019565
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.398	2204.704	.162	-.11143580	.07969963	-.26773000	.04485840
Job satisfaction with profession, teacher / Metric (All)	Equal variances assumed	1.289	.256	-.924	3247	.356	-.06157669	.06665962	-.19227587	.06912248
	Equal variances not assumed			-.916	2353.860	.360	-.06157669	.06722973	-.19341232	.07025894

This hypothesis aimed to investigate whether gender is differed in satisfaction working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession

Based on the how gender is differed in teachers job satisfaction with working environment. An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare teachers job satisfaction with environment within groups of Female and Male. There were significant differences ($t(2204.704) = -1.398, p=.162$) in the score with the mean score for Male ($M= 11.9554668, SD= 2.25814845$) was the highest than female ($M= 11.8440310, SD=2.02826036$). The magnitude of the differences in the mean difference= $-.11143580$, 95%CI: $-.26773000$ to 0.04485840 . Hence, H1 was supported and H0 was rejected.

However, the results from the group statistics based on the examination whether gender is differed in teachers job satisfaction with profession. The data presented in the table indicates that teachers job satisfaction with profession within groups of Female and Male. There were significant differences ($t(3247) = -.924, p=.356$) in the score with the mean score for Male ($M= M=11.4276835, SD=1.85818248$) was the highest than female ($M= 11.3661068, SD=1.80283529$). The magnitude of the differences in the mean difference= $-.06157669$, 95% CI: $-.19227587$ to 0.06912248 . Hence, H0 was rejected, and H1 was supported.

Therefore, there was a statistical mean difference gender in both teacher's job satisfaction working environment and teacher's job satisfaction with profession

iii. **H0** There is a significant model that predict satisfaction with working environment, teachers' satisfaction with profession, educational level, gender and age have an influence on teacher's job satisfaction

H1 There is no significant model that predict satisfaction with working environment, teachers' satisfaction with profession, educational level, gender and age have an influence on teacher's job satisfaction

Table 4.2.3: Multiple Linear Regression

Hypothesis	Regression Weight	Beta	R ²	t	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
	JS →JSWE	.586	.775	2.205	.000	H ₁
	JS→JSP	.586		1.902	.000	
F (1,3235)	11137.632					

*p<0.05.

JS: Job satisfaction; JSWE: Job Satisfaction with Working Environment; JSP: Job satisfaction with Profession

An investigation of Table 4.2.3 shown the two independent variable and controlling variables are significantly predictive of the dependent variable. Means that, Teachers satisfaction with environment, teachers' satisfaction with profession, educational level, gender and teachers age group significantly predicts teachers job satisfaction level in a school. The data presented $F(1,3235) = 11137.632$, $p < 0.005$, which specifies that the two independent variables has equal significant contribution on the teacher's job satisfaction. However, the $R^2 = .775$ depicts that the standard model identifies 77.5% of the variances in teachers job satisfaction.

Therefore, based on the multiple linear regression analysis results, the regression equation was obtained from the model which shown below; -

$$JS = -1.650 + 0.586JSWE + 0.586JSP + 5.756 \text{ Educ level} + 4.281 \text{ Gender} - 1.560 \text{ Teacher age}$$

5. Discussion

In this section, the findings are discussed in relation to research questions and reviewed relevant literature.

The study shown that there is correlation between teacher's satisfaction with working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession to secondary school teachers in Singapore secondary schools. The data indicated that $r = 0.477$ which is a positive correlation whereby apart from other factors teachers are also satisfied with working environment and satisfied with their teaching profession. TALIS 2013 and 2018 revealed the significant increase of 4% on how Singapore teachers valued and satisfied with teaching profession, as indicated positive correlation in the presented data (OCED, 2018). The studies of Crossman & Harris (2006) found that teachers are satisfied with in their teaching which incorporate supportive working environment and their professional growth. Renzulli, Parrott and Beattie (2011) shown that the positive teacher job satisfaction has a direct impact on students' academic achievement due to their increase of morale in their job. Moreover, Price & Collett (2012) stated that teachers' job satisfaction is vital because it has sturdy implications for teachers' attrition, retention, commitment towards education goals, and job performance. This findings comply with Tomazevic, Seljak & Aristovnik (2014), Sirin, (2009), Kumari, Joshi & Pandey (2014), Sohail & Huang (2013) and Sahito & Vaisanen (2017) who their studies identified

other factors that contribute to teachers job satisfaction such as teachers well-being, self-efficacy, workload, discipline, teaching practice.

Furthermore, there is a gender difference in satisfaction working environment and teacher's satisfaction with profession. The study indicated significant gender difference among Singapore teachers in their satisfaction with environment whereby male were more satisfied than female teachers score with the mean score of (M= 11.9554668, SD= 2.25814845, and for the female was (M= 11.8440310, SD=2.02826036). This indicates that there are some factors in the working environment which favor a male teacher than that female due to their needs, satisfaction level and well-being in the school. Similarly, to the other hypothesis which found that there is a difference for male and female teachers in satisfaction with profession. Still the mean score for male was higher than female teachers mean score. The mean score for (M= M=11.4276835, SD=1.85818248 and (M= 11.3661068, SD=1.80283529 correspondingly. There are several factors that contribute to teacher's satisfaction with profession for instance policies, school management, environment, well-being etc. Also, in Singapore 51% of male teachers are school leaders who are experienced in managerial role (OECD, 2018), this implies that they have satisfied more in their profession due to their responsibilities in the school.

Meanwhile, the findings of multiple linear regression from teacher's satisfaction with working environment, teachers' satisfaction with profession on job satisfaction. The study found that teacher's satisfaction with working environment and teachers' satisfaction with profession contribute at the same rate of 0.586 on teachers' job satisfaction in Singapore secondary schools. However, R² was 0.775 which is 77.5% on how the mentioned variables contribute on the teachers' job satisfaction. Similarly, to the study conducted by Houtte (2006); Johari et al (2018) discovered that the teachers working environment and teaching profession has a greater chance to predict teachers job satisfaction. Moreover, Osakwe (2014) stipulated that building a conducive working environment in teaching profession makes teacher to increase their job satisfaction level which boost their job performance hence it enhances productive return. Therefore, apart from other factors that contribute to the teachers' job satisfaction, the study has shown the same influence on the satisfaction with working environment and satisfaction with teaching profession.

6. Conclusion

This study showed that teacher's job satisfaction in Singapore secondary school has been contributed positively by teacher's working environment and teacher's profession. These factors shown how the school organization creates a good working environment for teachers which satisfy directly in their teaching profession. These findings revealed the needs for further studies to concentrate on investigating how other factors are positively correlate with teacher's job satisfaction in Singapore. The investigation will act as a lesson to other context which have low level of teacher's job satisfaction. Furthermore, it will enhance educational administrators, school principals and other educational stakeholders on creating conducive environment for teachers and add knowledge about teachers' job satisfaction. Moreover, a study recommended that apart from these factors assessed in this study, the further study can investigate on how teachers are satisfied by manipulating other factors on TALIS 2018 data.

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